

Determination of Glykitols and other Polyhydric Alcohols by Vanadium(V) in Perchloric Acid

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West and Skoog reported the determination of polyols by using sulphuric acid solution of vanadate¹. Other important methods involve the iodometric determinations after the oxidation of the substrate with pentavalent iodine^{2,3}, dichromate⁴, lead tetraacetate⁵, copper complex⁶, permanganate⁷, and cerate⁸. Pffaffenberger reviewed the analysis of sugar alcohols⁹. Recently, HPLC determination of sorbitol and mannitol¹⁰ and the development of a tubular periodate electrode for the determination of glycerol¹¹ have been reported. For the determination of mono- and disaccharides and sugar acids, vanadium(V) in dilute perchloric acid has been used¹²⁻¹⁴. We report here yet another application of the reagent for the determination of polyols.

Results and Discussion

The reduction of vanadate by polyols was complete in 1.5 h under reflux, yet the reaction time was fixed at 2 h to ensure complete oxidation of the substrate. Very accurate results were obtained when the vanadate solution was standardised by the same reductant¹³ (Table 1). The results of glycerol analysis by the present method exhibiting sharp and stable end point was compared with the well-known periodate method² which appeared to be unsatisfactory because of the detection of the end-point. Ethane-1, 2-diol could also be determined by the present method (Table 2). The vanadate solution was standardised against pure glucose by the procedure described before and the total quantity of the glycerol present in the unknown solution was determined using the conversion factor 0.7666. For sorbitol, mannitol and dulcitol the conversion factor was 0.8666 (Tables 1 and 2).

Inositol and propane-1,2-diol consumed vanadate very slowly while ethanol, 2-propanol, 1-butanol and 2-methyl-2-propanol remained practically unaffected by vanadate. Benzyl alcohol furnished a mixture of benzaldehyde and benzoic acid under the experimental condition. Hence the aforementioned compounds could not be determined by the present method.

Experimental

Sorbitol (Sigma) was dried under vacuum at 50° for 8 h before use. Mannitol, dulcitol (Sigma), glucose and inositol (Merck) were of analytical grade and stored over concentrated H₂SO₄ for at least 1 week before use. Glycerol,

ethylene glycol and other alcohols (Merck) were used as such. Sodium (or ammonium) metavanadate, perchloric acid (70%), potassium iodide, potassium dichromate and potassium periodate (all G.R., Merck), sodium thiosulphate and HCl (both A.R., Biosol) were used. The indicator was freshly prepared starch solution. Double-distilled water was used throughout.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF SORBITOL, MANNITOL AND DULCITOL IN SOLUTION OF UNKNOWN STRENGTH WITH VANADATE SOLUTION STANDARDISED BY RESPECTIVE SUGAR ALCOHOLS*

Sl. no.	Sorbitol (g dl ⁻¹) Actual/ (Found)	Mannitol (g dl ⁻¹) Actual/ (Found)	Dulcitol (g dl ⁻¹) Actual/ (Found)
1.	5.289 2 (5.105 5 ± 0.007 6)	1.848 0 (1.846 7 ± 0.004 5)	0.378 2 (0.381 6 ± 0.001 4)
2.	3.355 0 (3.357 3 ± 0.003 9)	1.311 6 (1.312 6 ± 0.002 4)	0.328 2 (0.325 6 ± 0.002 0)
3.	1.641 2 (1.632 9 ± 0.001 8)	1.071 6 (1.068 0 ± 0.001 4)	0.318 3 (0.315 0 ± 0.001 2)
4.	0.971 2 (0.973 2 ± 0.001 9)	0.911 6 (0.911 2 ± 0.003 2)	0.307 8 (0.304 8 ± 0.001 5)
5.	0.866 8 (0.864 7 ± 0.001 0)	0.702 3 (0.704 6 ± 0.005 7)	0.247 5 (0.251 3 ± 0.005 9)
6.	0.740 8 (0.737 9 ± 0.005 2)	0.554 0 (0.552 9 ± 0.001 4)	0.128 3 (0.127 3 ± 0.001 6)
7.	0.520 0 (0.520 9 ± 0.002 8)	0.405 7 (0.409 3 ± 0.001 8)	0.124 6 (0.125 6 ± 0.001 6)
8.	0.257 6 (0.263 2 ± 0.002 0)	0.215 7 (0.214 8 ± 0.001 3)	0.062 4 (0.063 4 ± 0.001 8)

*Results were 2-5% high with vanadate standardised by glucose, and using the conversion factor 0.8666; mean of six determinations ± standard deviation.

A stock solution of Na₂S₂O₃ (25 g/100 ml) was prepared and standardised iodometrically²; on requirement it was suitably diluted. A clear yellow solution of vanadium(V) (0.1 M) was obtained by adding slowly a cold solution of sodium (or ammonium) metavanadate (0.05 mol in 200 ml hot water) into a cold solution of perchloric acid (70%; 170 ml) in water (200 ml) whilst stirring continuously. This solution was standardised iodometrically^{12,13}.

Standardisation of the metavanadate solution with standard sorbitol solution. Determination of sorbitol in solution of unknown strength: To the aqueous solution (2 ml) of sorbitol (0.9355 g dl⁻¹), was added an excess of standard metavanadate solution (30 ml) and the reaction mix-

ture was refluxed. The residual vanadate was determined iodometrically^{12,13}. The above experiment was carried out without the reductant to determine the stability of vanadate solution under reflux during standardisation of the latter.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF DULCITOL (IN SOLID STATE), GLYCEROL AND ETHYLENE GLYCOL BY VANADATE SOLUTION STANDARDISED BY RESPECTIVE POLYOL

Sl. no.	Dulcitol (g Actual/Found)	Glycerol (g dl ⁻¹)* Actual/Found	Ethylene glycol (g dl ⁻¹) Actual/Found
1.	0.120 0 (0.120 9)	4.249 6 4.010 1 (3.981 6)	3.377 4 (3.283 2)
2.	0.093 8 (0.093 0)	2.134 0 2.062 7 (2.097 2)	1.528 3 (1.538 8)
3.	0.071 4 (0.071 3)	1.568 8 1.555 4 (1.458 8)	1.312 4 (1.316 8)
4.	0.054 6 (0.054 1)	0.849 9 0.862 6 (0.839 0)	0.873 2 (0.856 8)
5.	0.047 5 (0.047 6)	0.353 0 0.353 6 (0.373 2)	0.754 8 (0.747 2)
6.	0.041 5 (0.041 3)	0.231 2 0.227 4 (0.236 2)	0.436 4 (0.434 2)
7.	0.038 2 (0.038 1)	0.169 9 0.177 8 (0.161 4)	0.337 2 (0.334 8)
8.	0.014 1 (0.014 3)	0.050 1 0.052 6 (0.051 9)	0.218 4 (0.218 8)

*Results were 2–5% high with vanadate standardised by glucose and using the conversion factor 0.7666; Found by KIO₄ method in parenthesis.

When the vanadate solution was standardised by pure glucose¹² in the same procedure to determine the polyols, the errors were found to be comparatively larger. Solid sugar alcohols were determined following the aforementioned procedure but using 40–60 ml of metavanadate solution, depending on the material taken.

Product analysis : A known weight of the substrate was treated with an excess of the standard vanadate solution (known volume) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h and then the product was steam-distilled. The distillate responded strongly to the test of formic acid with mercuric chloride¹⁵ and quantitative determination revealed 95% recovery of the theoretical yield of formic acid¹⁴ (Table 3). But the test with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine sulphate confirmed the absence of formaldehyde or other carbonyl compound in the above distillate. In a separate experiment, a stream of CO₂-free nitrogen was bubbled through the refluxing reaction mixture, and the issuing gas was dried (H₂SO₄), then passed through the tared U-tubes containing soda-asbestos ("Carbosorb", 10–14 mesh, 63% Na₂O, B.D.H.). This experiment confirmed that CO₂ was not formed as a product of oxidation. Moreover, the issuing gas did not turn freshly prepared lime water milky.

A probable mechanism consistent with these observations and the calculated vanadate equivalent is schematically shown (Table 3). It was assumed in connection with the oxidation of sugar acids and related compound by vanadate(V) that a vanadate complex is formed in the transition state which undergoes fast decomposition to yield formic acid and a new product-substrate which reacts with fresh oxidant¹⁴. In all probability, the bright yellow vanadium(V) initially comes down to vanadium(III) which undergoes disproportionation¹⁶ with vanadium(V) to furnish deep blue vanadium(IV) as a stable compound.

TABLE 3—VANADATE EQUIVALENT OF THE POLYOLS

Substrate	Reaction
(i) Sorbitol/Mannitol/Dulcitol	$C_6H_{14}O_6 + 14A + 14H^+ = 6B + 14C + 8D$
(ii) Glucose	$C_6H_{12}O_6 + 12A + 12H^+ = 6B + 12C + 6D$
(iii) Glycerol	$C_3H_8O_3 + 8A + 8H^+ = 3B + 8C + 5D$
(iv) Ethylene glycol	$C_2H_6O_2 + 6A + 6H^+ = 2B + 6C + 4D$

A = VO₂⁺; B = HCOOH; C = VO²⁺, D = H₂O

Probable mechanism :

(c) One mole each of glykitols, glycerol and ethylene glycol required 14, 8 and 6 moles of vanadate respectively.

Calculation : If W is the concentration (g dl⁻¹) of the substrate in a solution, Z the titre value (ml) of thiosulphate solution required for the blank determination of V (ml) of the vanadate, and x and y are the titre values of the same thiosulphate required for the determination of the residual vanadate (from V ml) after the oxidation of the substrate of known and unknown strengths respectively, then the concentration of the substrate (S, g dl⁻¹) in the solution of unknown strength is given by $S = W(z - y)/(z - x)$.

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